

52°, the absorbance gradually decreases with the rise in temperature.

The interference of several cations and anions which often accompany ruthenium were examined by carrying out determinations of 3 ppm of ruthenium(III) in the presence of each of these ions. Results in Table 1 show that PCPMS is selective for ruthenium(III), but Pd(II), Os(VIII), Au(III), V(V), Ag(I) and iodide interfere strongly. The nature of the red species was studied by passing an aliquot of the solution of the species through cation exchange resin, Dowex 50W-X8 and anion exchange resin Dowex 1-X8. The red species was retained by Dowex 50W-X8 and not retained by Dowex 1-X8. This indicated that the species is cationic.

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An Indirect Method for Iodometric Microdetermination of Certain Organic Acids

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SINCE most carboxylic acids are weakly dissociated, their alkalimetry at micro level is confronted with two difficulties—poor inflection on the pH neutralisation curve which further contracts with increasing dilution of acid and alkali, and fading away of the phenolphthalein colour at the end-point¹.

Potentiometric location of the end-point is hampered owing to the formation of a buffer². The alkalimetry in non-aqueous medium has also been attempted using protophilic solvents, but in micro acidimetry the detection of the end-point is difficult.

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Further, titrants such as sodium triphenylmethyl and lithium aluminium hydride are too unstable to be used as 0.01 N standards¹.

The present communication describes a micro procedure which consists of heating the acid sample with iodide and a known excess of potassium iodate solution and subsequent iodometric determination of the surplus iodate. The quantity of acid present in the test solution is calculated from the amount of iodate consumed. The quantitative reaction is accomplished only in 3-5 min even with samples containing as low as 0.025 meq of the different organic acids studied. In order to ascertain suitable experimental conditions for the determination, the effect of change in the amount of iodide and iodate and in the reaction period in the case of each acid has also been investigated. On the basis of the results of these preliminary experiments a general procedure applicable for determining 0.025-0.1 meq of certain organic acids has been worked out.

Experimental

Reagents: The following solutions were prepared using analytical grade chemicals and conductive water. 0.1 N (0.0166 M) potassium iodate, which was also used to standardize the sodium thiosulphate solution (0.1 N). 0.01 and 0.005 N solutions were obtained by suitable dilution of the 0.1 N solutions. 0.05 N solutions of mono-, di- and tri-chloroacetic, furoic, sulphamic, β -chloropropionic, isobutyric, fumaric and benzoic acids were prepared and standardized by alkalimetry and diluted suitably to prepare the test solutions. In addition, 10% potassium iodide, 4 N sulphuric acid and 1% aqueous starch solutions were also prepared.

Procedure: An aliquot of an acid solution containing 0.025-0.1 meq of the acid is pipetted into a 100 ml erlenmeyer flask and 10 ml of 10% potassium iodide and 5-20 ml of 0.01 N potassium iodate solution (about 100% excess) are added. The flask is then kept immersed in a boiling water bath for 3-5 min after which it is cooled immediately under tap. 1 ml of starch solution is introduced and thiosulphate solution is added dropwise with constant shaking until the decolourisation of the blue colour. About 2 ml of 4 N sulphuric acid is then added and the liberated iodine is titrated with 0.01 or 0.005 N thiosulphate. A blank is also run. The difference between the blank and the experimental titres gives the amount of iodate used up. From this, the quantity of the acid present in the assay solution is calculated using the following relationships.

1 ml of 0.01 N thiosulphate = 0.45 mg of COOH group.

Results and Discussion

The proposed iodometric method has been applied for the determination of certain organic acids of varied nature. The recovery studies have been performed at three different concentration levels of each acid and the results recorded in Table 1 are the average of 6 determinations. Table 1 also gives a comparative study of errors observed in the alkalimetric and the proposed method for different acids studied. The average deviation in the latter method is in the range of 0.1-0.3%.

According to Smith³, a neutralisation indicator works satisfactorily only when the inflection or the pH neutralisation curve is more than 2 pH units. In titrating organic acids at micro level using 0.01 N alkali as the titrant, the inflection range is small. The difficulty in the detection of the end-point is further accentuated by the fading away of the phenolphthalein colour at the end-point. The alkalimetry of weak acids at micro level, therefore, gives a considerable positive error⁴.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CERTAIN ORGANIC ACIDS

Acid	Present mg	Alkalimetry		Iodometry	
		Found mg	% Average deviation	Found mg	% Average deviation
Acetic	6.000	6.030	+0.50	5.995	-0.08
	3.000	3.030	+1.00	3.003	+0.10
	1.500	1.527	+1.83	1.497	+0.20
Monochloroacetic	9.450	9.488	+0.40	9.459	+0.09
	4.725	4.764	+0.83	4.730	+0.10
	2.363	2.399	+1.50	2.359	-0.18
Dichloroacetic	12.900	12.913	+0.33	12.889	-0.08
	6.450	6.501	+0.81	6.461	+0.17
	3.225	3.268	+1.33	3.220	-0.15
Trichloroacetic	16.350	16.377	+0.16	16.337	-0.08
	8.175	8.216	+0.50	8.168	-0.08
	4.088	4.136	+1.17	4.094	+0.16
Furoic	11.208	11.245	+0.33	11.226	+0.16
	5.674	5.651	+0.81	5.595	-0.16
	2.837	2.814	+1.50	2.806	+0.16
Sulphamic	9.709	9.758	+0.50	9.718	+0.13
	4.855	4.887	+0.66	4.863	+0.16
	2.427	2.463	+1.50	2.423	-0.16
β -Chloropropionic	10.858	10.889	+0.33	10.835	-0.16
	5.426	5.480	+0.99	5.435	+0.16
	2.713	2.571	+1.40	2.723	+0.33
Isobutyric	8.810	8.869	+0.66	8.795	-0.16
	4.405	4.440	+1.00	4.390	-0.33
	2.203	2.240	+1.66	2.196	-0.33
Fumaric	5.803	5.822	+0.33	5.793	-0.16
	2.903	2.931	+1.00	2.897	0.16
	1.451	1.470	+1.33	1.446	-0.33
Benzilic	22.800	22.914	+0.50	22.819	+0.09
	11.400	11.514	+1.00	11.382	-0.16
	5.700	5.795	+1.66	5.681	-0.33

* Calculated from six determination.

In the case of titration with alkali the phenolphthalein colour fades rapidly at the end-point. The first appearance of the pink colour was noted.

Acids can also be determined by treating them with an excess of iodide and iodate solution followed by the titration of the liberated iodine

and this can be used as an alternative, often more accurate, to alkalimetry⁵. The iodometric method works well with strong acids but failed when applied to weak acids owing to slow reaction rate so that the reaction was not complete in 24 hr⁶. The reaction mixture could not be heated to speed up the determination on account of volatility of iodine. Recently, the addition of solid iodide and iodate has also been suggested for a direct iodometric determination of some organic acids⁷. Kolthoff⁸ suggested addition of a known excess of thiosulphate to acid solution containing iodide and iodate and subsequent back-titration of the surplus thiosulphate. But this procedure involves long reaction periods⁹. Moreover, there is a possibility of the thiosulphate reacting with the acid¹⁰ thus vitiating the stoichiometry of the main reaction.

The proposed method is based on the measurements of the iodate consumed rather than on the titration of the liberated iodine when an acid sample is treated with iodide and iodate. With this changed approach it is possible to heat the reaction mixture when the quantitative reaction can be achieved in 3-5 min with acid samples containing 0.025-0.1 meq of the acid. The procedure thus becomes rapid and being iodometric gives sharp end-point even when 0.01 or 0.005 N thiosulphate solution is used for titration. This iodometric method can also be adopted for determining acid content in various natural products which are slightly coloured, thereby rendering the neutralisation indicator unsuitable. In evaluating acid content of substances¹¹ containing components capable of reacting with alkali, the alkalimetry cannot yield correct results. In such cases also the proposed iodometric method possesses a distinct advantage.

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